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Simone Mora

simone.mora97@gmail.com

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-5260-8951>

Matteo Crotti

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Università di Pisa <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5913-3779>

Anna Pace

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4360-7668>

Giorgio Grioli

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Università di Pisa <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5310-2997>

Antonio Bicchi

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Università di Pisa <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8635-5571>

Maura Casadio

Università di Genova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2338-8995>

Manuel Giuseppe Catalano

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1950-6186>

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The SoftFoot Pro at the Cybathlon: Kinematic, Metabolic, and User Performance Evaluation

Simone Mora^{1*}, Matteo Crotti^{1,2}, Anna Pace¹, Giorgio Grioli^{1,2},
Antonio Bicchi^{1,2}, Maura Casadio³, Manuel Giuseppe Catalano¹

¹Soft Robotics for Human Cooperation and Rehabilitation, Istituto
Italiano di Tecnologia, Via S. Quirico 19D, Genova, 16163, Italy.

²Department of Information Engineering and Research Center “Enrico
Piaggio”, University of Pisa, Lungarno Antonio Pacinotti 43, Pisa,
56122, Italy.

³ Department of Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics and Systems
Engineering, University of Genova, Via All’Opera Pia 13, Genova,
16145, Italy.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): simone.mora97@gmail.com;

Contributing authors: matteo.crotti@iit.it; anna.pace@iit.it;
giorgio.grioli@iit.it; antonio.bicchi@unipi.it; maura.casadio@unige.it;
manuel.catalano@iit.it;

Abstract

Background:

Prosthetic feet are essential for restoring independent mobility in individuals with lower-limb loss. However, most commercial prosthetic feet rely on elastic elements and rigid, flat soles, limiting adaptability to uneven terrain and compromising user stability. Originally developed for robotic applications, the SoftFoot introduced an adaptive sole architecture inspired by the biomechanics of the human plantar fascia to improve ground conformity and gait stability. Building on this concept, we introduced the SoftFoot Pro at Cybathlon 2024 — a prosthetic counterpart that integrates a compliant adaptive sole with energy storage capabilities at the ankle joint through an agonist-antagonist mechanism. This design emulates the synergistic action of muscles, tendons, and the plantar fascia in the human shank-ankle-foot complex. This study evaluates the kinematic and metabolic performance of the SoftFoot Pro.

047 **Method:**
048 During a dedicated pre-competition training session, the official SoftFoot Pro
049 team pilot completed the Cybathlon Leg Race track twice using three prosthetic
050 feet: (i) the Triton foot (energy storage only), (ii) the original SoftFoot (adap-
051 tive sole only), and (iii) the SoftFoot Pro. Kinematic and metabolic data were
052 collected using the Xsens MVN Awinda and Cosmed K5 system. The evaluation
053 was complemented by questionnaires assessing locomotor performance, usability,
054 cognitive load, and user experience.

055 **Results:**
056 The SoftFoot Pro demonstrated greater ankle mobility than the original Soft-
057 Foot and the Triton across various tasks. Stride length and gait velocity were
058 comparable to the Triton and higher than with the original SoftFoot. The Soft-
059 Foot Pro revealed the fastest circuit completion time, with a metabolic cost of
060 transport comparable to the Triton and lower than the original SoftFoot. Ques-
061 tionnaires reported higher perceived mobility and lower cognitive and physical
062 effort with the SoftFoot Pro, compared to both the original SoftFoot and the
063 Triton, highlighting its functional and user experience advantages.

064 **Conclusions:**
065 This single-subject study quantitatively evaluated adaptive prosthetic feet in
066 Cybathlon tasks simulating daily activities. Integrating an ankle joint with an
067 agonist-antagonist energy recycling system improved mobility and reduced men-
068 tal and physical effort, matching the performance of commercial carbon fiber feet
069 while preserving the adaptive sole's advantages. The Cybathlon was the catalyst
070 for advancing the innovation and validation of our adaptive prosthesis.

071 **Keywords:** Foot Prosthesis, Adaptive Foot, Metabolic Analysis, Kinematic Analysis,
072 Cybathlon

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1 Background

Living with a disability is a severe condition for many people, as they often do not have equal access to health care, education, and employment opportunities, and frequently experience exclusion from everyday life activities [1]. According to [1], approximately 18% of the global population suffers from some form of disability, with limb loss being a prevalent condition that significantly affects an individual's ability to perform daily tasks. This often leads to physical inactivity, resulting in cardiovascular diseases, muscle atrophy, joint stiffness, obesity, and depression [2]. Around 38 million people worldwide are affected by major amputations, with 85% of individuals experiencing lower limb amputations [3]. In the United States, around 61% of amputations involve

at least one foot [4]. These statistics have driven research into the development of lower limb prosthetic devices, particularly focusing on the foot unit, which must efficiently absorb forces during the gait cycle, withstand body weight, and provide stability for maintaining a well-balanced posture and preventing musculoskeletal imbalances [5].

Recent advancements in materials technology have facilitated the transition from prosthetic feet suitable for individuals belonging to the K1 functional classification, typically characterized by a wooden keel, e.g. Solid Ankle Cushioned Heel (SACH) and Single Axis feet, to carbon fiber prosthetic feet with energy-storage-and-return (ESR) capabilities, associated with the K3 and K4 classifications [6, 7]. This evolution has facilitated the completion of more complex tasks, beyond simple locomotion on level surfaces at a fixed cadence, such as stair climbing and slope navigation. It has reduced walking costs [8], also expanding the opportunities to participate in sports, from recreational and rehabilitative activities to high-level competition, including the Paralympic Games, favoring an increase in societal integration among people with limb deficiencies by improving mental well-being and boosting self-confidence [9].

Although ESR feet represent an effective solution for individuals with lower-limb amputations, they do not fully reproduce the complex biomechanics and rich articulation of the human foot, and therefore still present significant limitations with important consequences for users. Their prolonged use is a major contributing factor to conditions such as osteoarthritis and osteoporosis due to musculoskeletal imbalances [5]. Furthermore, the risk of falls remains a serious and unresolved issue for prosthetic users [10, 11], posing a major challenge to the scientific community, as highlighted in [12, 13].

In [14], we analyzed how rigid and flat soles, which do not conform to uneven surfaces, reduce the walking support area and compromise stability when encountering non-flat obstacles. Consequently, we introduced the concept of a passive adaptive prosthetic foot that more closely mimics the functionality of the human ankle-foot

139 system. This approach has been shown to improve stability in bipedal walking, as
140 demonstrated in [15], where the SoftFoot was introduced as a robotic foot for humanoid
141 robots.
142 robots.

144 In this context, we developed a novel prosthetic foot, the SoftFoot Pro, inspired
145 by the original robotic design. It features a compliant sole architecture that increases
146 the contact surface and conforms to ground irregularities, mimicking the behavior of
147 the human foot [14]. However, in translating the concept from robotics to prosthetic
148 applications, it was necessary also to address the challenge of generating push-off
149 power — a need not present in bipedal robots with actuated joints. To overcome this,
150 a passive agonist-antagonist mechanism inspired by human anatomy was integrated
151 at the ankle joint, enabling energy storage and return during gait while preserving
152 ground adaptability [16]. This combined approach aims to reduce user fatigue, improve
153 forward propulsion, and emulate the synergistic action of the human shank-ankle-foot
154 complex. With the SoftFoot Pro, we successfully participated in the Cybathlon 2024
155 Leg Prosthesis Race, achieving second place. As is well known, the Cybathlon is an
156 international competition where individuals with physical disabilities compete using
157 advanced assistive technologies. In the Leg Prosthesis Race, pilots perform a series of
158 everyday mobility tasks designed to test balance, adaptability, and overall prosthetic
159 functionality, closely reflecting real-world challenges [17, 18].

170 This study evaluates the kinematic and metabolic performance of the novel agonist-
171 antagonist SoftFoot Pro (combining energy storage and adaptive sole features) in
172 comparison to commercial carbon fiber feet (energy storage only) and the original Soft-
173 Foot (adaptive sole only). User impressions and experiences were also assessed. The
174 analysis was conducted with the official pilot of the SoftFoot Pro team during a ded-
175 icated pre-competition training session. The pilot completed the full Cybathlon Leg
176 Prosthesis Race track twice consecutively. An in-depth kinematic analysis was carried
177 out for both the level walking and stair-walking tasks of the Cybathlon, focusing on
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lower-limb joint range of motion and providing a detailed description of joint angle patterns in the sagittal plane. Gait symmetry and walking speed were also evaluated across the three prosthetic feet. In addition, a more general kinematic assessment was performed by analyzing the maximum angular excursions at each lower-limb joint. The comprehensive kinematic and metabolic assessments demonstrated that the agonist-antagonist SoftFoot Pro significantly improved performance compared to the original SoftFoot across a wide range of demanding locomotor tasks requiring functional capabilities beyond simple level-ground ambulation, while achieving similar performance to the commercial carbon fiber foot. Specifically, it resulted in a reduced net metabolic cost of walking — comparable to that of the carbon fiber foot — and an increased ankle joint range of motion relative to both the original SoftFoot and the carbon fiber foot. Finally, the novel SoftFoot Pro showed the fastest track completion time and robust performance across diverse tasks. Questionnaire results further confirmed the pilot’s positive perception of stability, comfort, and overall usability, even with respect to the carbon fiber foot.

This single-subject case study provided a quantitative evaluation of novel adaptive prosthetic feet during Cybathlon tasks, which closely replicate everyday activities. Our findings suggest that integrating an ankle joint with an agonist-antagonist energy recycling system offers substantial benefits for users in real-world applications, achieving performance comparable to commercial carbon fiber feet while preserving the advantages of an adaptive sole. The Cybathlon thus served as a crucial catalyst for advancing both the innovation and validation of our adaptive prosthesis.

2 Methods

2.1 Participant

The participant, an official pilot in the Cybathlon 2024 Leg Prosthesis Race, was a 56-year-old male, 1.74 m tall and weighing 75 kg. He had a unilateral transfemoral

231 amputation on the right side resulting from an accident at the age of 47 and belonged to
232 the K3-K4 functional classification. During the training and the competition, the pilot
233 wore a semi-active knee system, the Genium by Ottobock (Duderstadt, Germany), the
234 same prosthetic knee he wore daily. The carbon fiber foot used in the experimental ses-
235 sion was the Triton by Ottobock (Duderstadt, Germany), the commercially available
236 passive ESR foot that the user wore daily.

241 To provide a visual reference of typical joint behavior in the absence of prosthetic-
242 related issues, the performance of an unimpaired (non-amputee) subject (26 years old,
243 1.80 m tall, 76 kg, Male) was recorded with the same set-up and condition during two
244 tasks: level walking and stair ascending-descending.

247 Testing was conducted after the subjects were fully informed about the study’s
248 aims and procedures and provided written informed consent to the experimental activ-
249 ity. The study was approved by the Bioethical Committee of the University of Pisa
250 (resolution no. 48/2024).

255 **2.2 Experimental Setup**

258 **2.2.1 SoftFootPro**

259 The SoftFoot (Fig. 1, left panels) is a passive, underactuated, anthropomorphic, and
260 adaptive foot inspired by the complex architecture and functions of the human foot
261 [14]. Its design aims to reproduce the ability of the human foot to adapt to the differ-
262 ent grounds we encounter daily with its articulated structure of bones, tendons, and
263 muscles, and its ability to stiffen to act as a rigid lever when propelling the body for-
264 ward [19]. The SoftFoot compliance is determined by the underactuated sole, designed
265 to provide adaptability on uneven terrains. The sole features five flexible parallel plan-
266 tar modules, each made of smaller units coupled with Hillberry joints, going from heel
267 to toe. Adjacent units are connected with elastic bands, and an inextensible tendon
268 routes following a specific path through each module, giving the foot a stress-stiffening
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Fig. 1 SoftFoot models and prototypes. The top row shows, on the left, the model of the original SoftFoot and, on the right, that of the agonist-antagonist SoftFoot Pro used at Cybathlon. The bottom row shows the corresponding prototypes.

behavior. In this way, the structure is compliant under low loads, and it stiffens under higher loads, effectively supporting the user's weight throughout the gait cycle. Two rigid elements, the rear and the frontal arches, connect the sole to the user's pilon.

The SoftFoot Pro, shown on the right side of Fig. 1, improves the original SoftFoot by incorporating a passive agonist-antagonist ankle mechanism that enables the system to store and release energy in response to the user's load throughout the gait cycle. This mechanism introduces an anterior and a posterior spring set, with respect to the ankle joint, connecting the arches and the shank. The shank link (AlSi10Mg) is free to rotate about the ankle joint and is connected to the pilon, enabling a more natural ankle motion and effectively transmitting the mechanical action of the springs to the user. The anterior spring set, two elastic bungee cords (from Sandow Technic, Germany), replicates the function of the dorsiflexor muscles in human walking, aiding in shock absorption during the loading response phase. Conversely, the posterior spring, a customized S-shaped titanium spring (Ti6Al4V), mimics the behavior of the

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323 Achilles tendon and plantarflexor muscles, reducing energy dissipation and thereby
324 enhancing walking efficiency. This prototype represents a redesigned version of the
325 device presented in [16], specifically developed for the Cybathlon competition. This
326 updated design aims to achieve a more compact and user-friendly solution, keeping the
327 same core architecture but with a more functional physical implementation to make
328 it more suitable for everyday use and for the competition.
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334 **2.2.2 Data Acquisition**

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336 Lower-limb kinematics were recorded using a portable, wireless, inertial kinematic
337 measurement system (Xsens MVN Awinda system, Movella, Henderson, USA). This
338 system was preferred over traditional optical motion capture systems, which require
339 the placement of predefined markers that could be displaced during the dynamic activ-
340 ities and demand specific environmental conditions for camera calibration and optimal
341 functionality [20]. Marker occlusions also pose a significant limitation in such setups.
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343 Kinematic data were collected at 100 Hz using 7 Inertial Measurement Units (IMU)
344 (dimensions: 47 mm × 30 mm × 13 mm; weight: 20 g) positioned on the feet, lower
345 legs, upper legs, and pelvis, following the Xsens setup guidelines (see Fig. 2) [21, 22].
346 Before data acquisition, the subject’s body measurements were registered and set on
347 the system software, and a sensor-to-segment calibration was performed while the
348 participant stood in a predefined pose (i.e., N-pose, with the arms along the trunk).
349 The acquisition scenario was configured to “Multilevel” mode in the Xsens software
350 to account for the subject’s interaction with flat and varying-height terrains.
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352 The metabolic data were recorded with the Cosmed K5 (COSMED, Italy), a
353 portable metabolic analyzer used to measure respiratory gases and assess energy
354 expenditure during rest or physical activity in clinical, sports, and research settings.
355 The calibration process included flowmeter calibration, scrubber reset, and reference
356 gas calibration to compensate for potential environmental factors affecting turbine
357 accuracy, to zero the CO₂ analyzer, and to set gas concentrations to known reference
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Fig. 2 The figure shows frontal and rear views of the subject equipped with all the sensors: IMU in orange and the K5 metabolic analyzer.

values [23]. A face mask, equipped with the flowmeter, was securely fitted to the subject using adjustable elastic bands and a harness, supporting the main unit of the system, weighing less than 1 kg, positioned on the back of the user, as in Fig. 2. The system operated in Telemetry Data Transmission mode, transmitting data wirelessly to a dedicated PC station.

2.2.3 Leg Prosthesis Race

The race consisted of ten tasks designed to simulate everyday challenges faced by individuals with lower limb loss. They are presented in the order in which they were completed during the Zurich competition in Fig. 3. We reproduced the setup in our laboratory according to the instructions for the materials and equipment reported in [18]. A more detailed description of the tasks and the rules for their invalidation can be found at [18]. An additional video file demonstrates the fitting process of the SoftFoot

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439 **Fig. 3** Cybathlon 2024: Tasks. The figure shows the ten Cybathlon 2024 tasks as performed by the
440 SoftFoot Pro team pilot during the final, along with the setup of each task. The top row, from left
441 to right, shows the Balance beam, Stairs, Step over, Slopes and Bench and table tasks. The bottom
442 row, from left to right, shows the Wobbly steps, High step, Ladder, Cross country and Hurdles tasks.

443 prosthesis, its integration into daily activities, and its application during both training
444 and the official competition (see Additional File 1).

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447 **2.3 Experimental protocol**

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449 Data collection was conducted in a spacious laboratory room set up to replicate all
450 tasks from the official Leg Race discipline of the Cybathlon 2024 event; no other
451 wireless devices were present that could interfere with the data recording. Initially, the
452 calibration procedures required for the Cosmed K5 (flowmeter calibration, scrubber
453 reset, and reference gas calibration) were completed. The subject was familiarized
454 with the measurement devices and then equipped with the IMU sensors. Once the
455 IMUs calibration phase was performed, the subject was equipped with the Cosmed K5.
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The subject was asked to complete two consecutive rounds of the Cybathlon circuit following the competition task order at a competition-like pace with three different prosthetic feet: the Triton foot, the SoftFoot Pro, and the original SoftFoot, in this exact order. Two rounds were required to make the trial long enough to reach a metabolic steady state condition. No familiarization phase was required on the test day for the prosthetic devices, as the subject had already become extensively familiar with them during multiple training sessions in the weeks leading up to the test day. The experiment continued even if errors occurred that would have invalidated a specific task. For each tested foot, the subject was initially asked to rest for 5 minutes on a chair to acquire resting metabolic data. He then completed two rounds of the Cybathlon circuit without breaks and finally performed three repetitions of walking on level ground along a seven-meter path. A five-minute break followed. The foot was then changed, and the protocol restarted.

When changing the foot, the participant completed four standardized questionnaires to provide qualitative feedback on the three tested prosthetic feet. These included:

- **Prosthetic Evaluation Questionnaire (PEQ):** Comprising nine validated multi-item scales, plus additional individual questions. Mobility was assessed using the Locomotion scale (8 questions) and five questions under the Transfer category [24].
- **Locomotor Capabilities Index (LCI-5):** A self-reported measure of prosthetic mobility, designed to assess walking ability. It uses five response levels (0 to 4), with the original third level divided into two categories for greater detail [gailey:2012, 25].
- **System Usability Scale (SUS):** A five-point Likert scale that measures the perceived usability of each prosthetic foot [26, 27].

507 • **NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX)**: A five-point Likert scale used to
508 evaluate perceived cognitive and physical workload across multiple independent
509 dimensions [28, 29].
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513 **2.4 Data analysis**

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515 During preliminary trials, in Task 5, “Bench and Table”, the subject accidentally
516 bumped the table while sitting on the bench, due to the small distance between them,
517 causing an undesired change in the position of IMU sensors, thus altering data acqui-
518 sition. Therefore, this task was excluded from the official testing session, and the
519 analysis presented in this study includes only nine of the ten Cybathlon 2024 Leg Race
520 tasks. Kinematic and metabolic analyses were conducted using MATLAB R2023b.
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526 **2.4.1 Kinematic Analysis**

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528 Hip, knee, and ankle raw signals were extracted from both the intact limb (IL) and
529 the prosthetic limb (PL). The analysis was conducted across three key domains: level
530 walking, stair ascent and descent, and the complete set of nine Cybathlon tasks.
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532 All kinematic and spatio-temporal parameters described below were compared across
533 the three tested prosthetic feet. As the data were collected from a single subject,
534 comparisons were made for visual inspection only, and no statistical analysis was
535 performed.
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541 ***Level Walking task***

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543 Gait cycles immediately preceding or following a change in walking direction were
544 excluded to avoid transitional effects. Ten gait cycles per limb were time-normalized
545 to express each angular trajectory as a percentage of the gait cycle. Each angular sig-
546 nal was resampled to yield 150 data points uniformly distributed across the gait cycle.
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548 For each joint and limb, the mean and standard deviation of the angular trajectories
549 were computed and compared across the three types of prosthetic feet. Additionally,
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the kinematic analysis included calculation of joint range of motion (ROM) — defined as the average across gait cycles of the difference between the maximum and minimum joint angles within each cycle. Mean stride length and gait speed were also computed for each prosthetic foot condition, averaged over four consecutive gait cycles, selected to exclude steps involving a change of walking direction, and normalized to the subject’s body height (BH).

Stairs task

Following the extraction of raw angular signals, only the central gait cycles were selected for analysis. This approach minimized the variability typically associated with initiation and termination steps, while also reducing potential signal distortions arising from compensatory movements, such as those adopted by the participant to stabilize the tray with the cup during the task. Specifically, three gait cycles were analyzed during ascent and three during descent for each limb, corresponding to the middle steps of the ramp. Each angular trajectory was time-normalized and resampled to 150 data points, representing 0–100% of the gait cycle.

Cyathlon tasks

For all Cyathlon tasks, the maximum angular excursion was obtained as the difference between the maximum and minimum joint angle values recorded during the entire execution of each task. The completion time of each task and the total time for the circuit were obtained directly from the Xsens software.

2.4.2 Metabolic Analysis

For the metabolic analysis, six minutes were necessary to reach the metabolic plateau after the transient phase, allowing for an accurate examination of the subject’s metabolic response under exertion. For this reason, two consecutive rounds of the Cyathlon race were performed.

599 The rate of oxygen consumption (VO_2) and the Respiratory Exchange Ratio
600 (RER), provided by the Cosmed K5 system as the ratio between carbon dioxide pro-
601 duced to oxygen consumed, were extracted during both the resting phase and the
602 activity plateau phase. VO_2 data were normalized to the subject's body mass, and
603 mean values were computed for both the resting phase and the second round of the
604 Cybathlon. Subsequently, the Net Cost of Transport (NCoT) was calculated for each
605 of the three prosthetic foot designs to compare the metabolic demands required to
606 complete the activities using the following equation:
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$$613 \quad NCoT = \frac{EEq - RMR}{WS \times 60}. \quad (1)$$

614 where EEq is the Energetic Equivalent of the oxygen consumed in [$J/kg/min$], RMR
615 is the Resting Metabolic Rate, i.e., the energy consumption at rest [$J/kg/min$], and
616 WS is the walking speed [m/s] [30]. The EEq is calculated as:
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$$621 \quad EEq = (15962 + 5155 \times RER_{cyb}) \left(\frac{VO_{2cyb}}{1000} \right) \quad (2)$$

622 where RER_{cyb} is the mean value of the RER during the Cybathlon second round, and
623 VO_{2cyb} is the mean value of the VO_2 during the Cybathlon second round. While the
624 RMR is defined as:
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$$627 \quad RMR = (15962 + 5155 \times RER_{rest}) \left(\frac{VO_{2rest}}{1000} \right) \quad (3)$$

628 where RER_{rest} is the mean value of the RER during the resting phase, and VO_{2rest} is
629 the mean value of the VO_2 during the resting phase. Finally, Heart Rate (HR) was also
630 monitored throughout the activity to provide complementary data on cardiovascular
631 effort.
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2.4.3 Questionnaires and Cybathlon performance

The pilot was asked to complete four questionnaires, as previously mentioned in 2.3.

The first one was the PEQ, consisting of 82 items. The participant rated each of the three prosthetic feet using a 100-*mm* analog scale. Scale scores were calculated as the arithmetic mean of all answered items within each scale, provided that at least half of the items were completed, and then expressed on a 0–100 scale.

The second questionnaire was the LCI-5, comprising 14 items, scored from 0 to 4 (0 = no; 1 = yes, with help; 2 = yes, with supervision; 3 = yes, alone with aids; 4 = yes, alone without aids). Basic and advanced mobility subscale scores were computed separately by summing the responses to their respective 7 items, each expressed out of a maximum of 28 points. The total LCI-5 score was obtained by summing these subscale scores and reported out of 56.

The SUS and NASA-TLX questionnaires were also administered to evaluate perceived usability and workload for each prosthetic foot. For the SUS, the participant rated 10 items on a 5-point Likert scale (1 to 5). Scores for odd-numbered items were recalculated by subtracting 1, while scores for even-numbered items were recalculated by subtracting the score from 5. The adjusted scores were summed and multiplied by 2.5 to yield a total SUS score out of 100 per prosthesis. The six subscales of the NASA-TLX were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 to 5), with results visualized using radar charts.

In addition to questionnaire data, a performance analysis of the final race of the 2024 Cybathlon Leg Race final was conducted by comparing task completion times and success rates across the four finalist teams. User feedback on both the original SoftFoot and the SoftFoot Pro was collected during training and post-competition debriefings.

691 **3 Results**

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694 **3.1 Kinematics**

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696 **3.1.1 Level walking**

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698 Fig.4 shows the sagittal plane joint angle patterns (ankle, knee, and hip) for the
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700 prosthetic limb and the intact limb during level walking, stair ascent, and stair descent.

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702 The ranges of motion of the same joints are presented in Fig. 5, with mean values

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704 reported in Table 1.

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706 During level walking, the biological ankle exhibited average plantarflexion and

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708 dorsiflexion peaks of approximately 4° and 16°, respectively, during the early and

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710 late stance phases. In the swing phase (60% - 100% of the gait cycle), the average

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712 plantarflexion peak reached approximately 16°. The knee exhibited average flexion

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714 peak of approximately 18° during the stance phase and 65° during the swing phase.

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716 During early stance, the subject's prosthetic ankle reached an average plantarflex-

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718 ion peak of 2° with the original Softfoot, 6° with Triton, and 8° when exploiting the

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720 Softfoot Pro. At the end of the stance, the mean value of dorsiflexion peak was 8°

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722 with the original Softfoot, 13° with Triton, and 19° with the Softfoot Pro. All three

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724 feet showed no plantarflexion movement during the swing phase. At the sound ankle,

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726 the average plantarflexion peak in early stance was 6° across all prosthetic feet, while

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728 the average dorsiflexion peak in late stance was 13° with the original SoftFoot and

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730 Triton, and increased to 15° with the SoftFoot Pro. Furthermore, the Triton and the

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732 SoftFoot Pro exhibited greater peak plantarflexion at mid-swing, with average values

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734 of 27° and 29°, respectively, while the original SoftFoot reached only 21°.

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736 The knee joint angle in the prosthetic limb exhibited a flat pattern throughout the

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738 entire stance phase when using the Triton and SoftFoot Pro, whereas with the original

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740 SoftFoot this flat pattern, observed only in 0% - 20% of the gait cycle, was followed

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742 by a prolonged hyperextension during late stance (30% - 50% of the gait cycle), just

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Fig. 4 Sagittal plane ankle, knee and hip angle patterns of the prosthetic limb (PL) and intact limb (IL). From left to right, level walking (mean value from 10 strides), stairs ascent (3 steps), and stairs descent (3 steps) angles are reported for the Cybathlon pilot using the three different feet: Triton (red), original SoftFoot (green), and SoftFoot Pro (blue). The joint angles of an unimpaired subject are shown for comparison (black).

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Fig. 5 Ankle, knee, and hip ROM values of the Cybathlon pilot's prosthetic limb and intact limb during level walking (LW), stairs ascent (U), and stairs descent (D). Bars represent the different prosthetic feet: Triton (red), original SoftFoot (green), and SoftFoot Pro (blue).

Table 1

Limb	Joints	Tasks	Prosthetic feet			
			Triton [°]	Original SoftFoot [°]	SoftFoot Pro [°]	
PL	Ankle	Level walking	19.9	10.4	27.8	
		Stairs ascent	5.1	7.8	8.4	
		Stairs descent	7.0	10.4	15.2	
	Knee	Level walking	59.1	54.3	54	
		Stairs ascent	91.8	85.7	84.7	
		Stairs descent	62.6	67.5	62.4	
		Hip	Level walking	41.8	36.1	42.6
			Stairs ascent	64.9	69	66.9
			Stairs descent	26.3	29.9	31.5
IL	Ankle	Level walking	41.5	36.3	46.7	
		Stairs ascent	44.7	41.5	48	
		Stairs descent	59.6	49	60.3	
	Knee	Level walking	55.9	53.4	56.1	
		Stairs ascent	76	78.7	81.4	
		Stairs descent	72.1	66.6	76.2	
		Hip	Level walking	36.6	33.9	39.2
			Stairs ascent	57.8	56.7	55.1
			Stairs descent	25.6	29.8	25.3

Mean ROM values for lower limb joints of both the prosthetic and intact limbs during Level walking and Stairs task from the Cybathlon event. Comparison among the three tested prosthetic feet.

before the flexion peak in the swing phase, with an average hyperextension peak of 3°. In the intact limb, the early stance flexion peak (12% of the gait cycle) was absent when using the original SoftFoot and Triton, unlike the SoftFoot Pro (average peak of 6°).

The prosthetic hip remained consistently more flexed than that of the unimpaired subject.

From the ROM analysis emerged that the prosthetic ankle achieved an average ROM of 27.8° when the Softfoot Pro was used, which was about 40% higher than the Triton (19.9°) and approximately 167% greater than the original SoftFoot (10.4°). At

875 the knee and hip joints of both the prosthetic and the intact limb, differences between
 876 ROM values were less marked across different prosthetic feet.
 877

878 Finally, Table 2 reports the mean and standard deviation values for stride length
 879 and gait speed during level walking, normalized to the subject’s height and expressed
 880 as percentages, for both the Cybathlon pilot and the unimpaired subject. The unim-
 881 paired subject exhibited an average stride length value of 1.2 meters and an average
 882 walking speed of 0.92 m/s. Stride length values were comparable between the pros-
 883 thetic limb and the intact limb across all three prosthetic feet. The Triton and the
 884 SoftFoot Pro feet showed an average stride length of 1.2 meters for both the prosthetic
 885 and intact limbs. The original SoftFoot resulted in a stride length of 1.0 meter. The
 886 average walking speeds, expressed in m/s, were 0.95 for the Triton and the SoftFoot
 887 Pro, 0.75 for the original SoftFoot.
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896 3.1.2 Stairs Task

897 During stair ascent, the biological ankle began with 20° of dorsiflexion and reached
 898 a peak plantarflexion of approximately 10° at the end of the stance phase. The knee
 899 and hip exhibited a similar pattern: they started with approximately 60° and 50° of
 900 flexion, respectively, followed by an extension movement during the stance phase and
 901 a subsequent flexion during the swing phase.
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906 **Table 2**

907 Subjects	908 Prosthetic Foot	909 Stride Length/BH [%]		910 Gait Speed/BH [% s ⁻¹]
		911 PL	912 IL	
913 Pilot	914 Triton	68.2 ± 4.0	69.3 ± 1.5	54.5 ± 3.7
	915 Original SoftFoot	60.1 ± 1.6	60.3 ± 1.2	43.2 ± 2.6
	916 SoftFoot Pro	71.0 ± 3.7	70.7 ± 2.7	54.3 ± 5.4
917 Unimpaired subject		69.2 ± 2.2		52.7 ± 1.9

918 Mean and standard deviation values for stride length (PL = prosthetic limb; IL = intact limb) and
 919 average gait velocity (normalized to body height and expressed as a percentage) during level walking.
 920 Data are reported for the Cybathlon pilot using the three tested prosthetic feet, as well as for the
 unimpaired subject.

With all three prosthetic feet, the prosthetic ankle maintained a neutral position during both the loading response and swing phases, showing limited dorsiflexion motion at the end of the stance, with different patterns observed across the three prosthetic feet. The prosthetic knee started with approximately 40° of flexion, with minimal variation across feet and steps, and remained in a more extended position throughout the stance phase, reaching a neutral configuration. The prosthetic hip remained consistently more flexed than the biological hip, especially at initial contact and during terminal swing.

During stair descent, the unimpaired subject initiated the gait cycle with approximately 20° of plantarflexion and reached a peak dorsiflexion of about 30° during the stance phase. In the 0% and 40% interval of the gait cycle, the prosthetic ankle exhibited reduced dorsiflexion, with peak values varying depending on the prosthetic foot. During the swing phase, the prosthetic ankle returned to a neutral position across all three prosthetic feet, without showing plantarflexion. The biological ankle reached 20° of plantarflexion to initiate the subsequent step. The unimpaired subject showed greater knee flexion, while the Cybathlon pilot exhibited increased hip flexion.

Joint angle patterns were generally similar between the participant's intact limb and the unimpaired subject, with the participant's sound limb exhibiting a greater overall range of motion.

The analysis of the range of motion revealed that in the stair ascent task, the SoftFoot Pro achieved a ROM of 8.4°, representing a 65% increase over the Triton (5.1°) and an 8% increase over the original SoftFoot (7.8°). In stairs descent, the SoftFoot Pro reached a ROM value of 15.2°, marking a 117% increase compared to the Triton (7.0°) and a 46% increase over the original SoftFoot (10.4°). The knee and hip joints of both the prosthetic and intact limbs exhibit comparable ranges of motion.

967 **3.1.3 Cybathlon tasks: Maximum angular excursion**

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969 For all the Cybathlon’s tasks of the Leg Race performed during the circuit, an over-
970 all assessment of lower limb kinematics was conducted by evaluating the maximum
971 angular excursion for the ankle, knee, and hip joints for both limbs.
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974 At the ankle joint (top panel of Fig. 6), the angular excursion of the prosthetic ankle
975 was the highest when using the SoftFoot Pro across most tasks; the only exceptions
976 were during the High Step and Cross Country tasks. Conversely, the original SoftFoot
977 exhibited the lowest angular excursion across all tasks, except for the Cross Country
978 task, where its amplitude was comparable to both the Triton foot and the SoftFoot
979 Pro, and the Stairs task, where it was similar to the Triton foot.
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984 At the knee joint (middle panel of Fig. 6), the greatest angular excursions were
985 required for Stairs, High Step, Ladder, and Hurdles tasks, while Cross Country, Wob-
986 bly Steps, and Slopes elicited the smallest amplitude of motion. The prosthetic knee
987 achieved the highest flexion in 6 out of the 9 tasks, reaching approximately 90 degrees
988 in four of them—Hurdles, Ladder, High Step, and Stairs—when using the Triton foot.
989 The other two feet showed overall reduced knee flexion in these tasks compared to the
990 Triton foot, but greater knee flexion during Wobbly Steps and Step Over.
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994 At the hip joint (bottom panel of Fig. 6), the most notable result was the high
995 degree of flexion observed in both the sound and prosthetic limbs, across all three
996 prosthetic feet and in all tasks —except for the Wobbly Step, which showed flexion
997 values more comparable to those typically seen during level walking.
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1000 **3.2 Task performance: completion times**

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1002 The times required to complete each task, as well as the total time for the second lap
1003 of the circuit, are reported in Table 3. The SoftFoot Pro was the fastest in six out of
1004 nine tasks, achieving a total completion time of 290 seconds. The overall completion
1005 times were 295 seconds for the original SoftFoot and 310 seconds for the Triton.
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Fig. 6 Angular excursion at the ankle (top), knee (middle), and hip (bottom) joints of the prosthetic limb (dark bars) and the intact limb (light bars) during all Cybathlon tasks performed by the pilot. Different prosthetic feet are represented by color-coded bars: Triton (red), original SoftFoot (green), and SoftFoot Pro (blue).

1059 **Table 3**

1060 1061	Cyathlon tasks	Prosthetic feet		
		1062 Triton [s]	Original SoftFoot [s]	SoftFoot Pro [s]
1063	Balance Beam	30.1	32.7	29.3
1064	Stairs	33.5	33.2	34.8
1065	Step Over	42.7	44.7	35.1
1066	Slopes	27	26	24.2
1067	Wobbly Steps	8.3	9.5	8.2
1068	High Step	24.2	20.9	19.5
1069	Ladder	25.3	18.1	18.8
1070	Cross Country	24	20	29.1
1071	Hurdles	40.8	36	35.5
1072	Total	310	295	290

1073 Completion times in seconds for the nine Cyathlon tasks and the overall second circuit lap for each
1074 of the three tested prosthetic feet.

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1078 **3.3 Metabolic cost**

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1080 Table 4 presents the main metabolic parameters calculated for the second circuit lap
1081 with the three feet.

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Specifically, the $VO_{2\text{plateau}}$ values were 18.8, 19.9, and 18.7 [mL/(kg*min)] for the Triton, the original SoftFoot, and the SoftFoot Pro, respectively. The NCoT parameter exhibited values of 5.4 and 5.6 [J/(kg*m)] for the Triton and the SoftFoot Pro, respectively, approximately 30% lower than the value reported for the original SoftFoot (7.9 [J/(kg*m)]). Furthermore, the RER value remained below one throughout the physical activity for all three prosthetic feet.

1092 **Table 4**

1093 1094	Parameters	Prosthetic feet		
		1095 Triton	Original SoftFoot	SoftFoot Pro
1096	$VO_{2\text{plateau}}$ [mL/(kg*min)]	18.8	19.9	18.7
1097	RER_{plateau}	0.9	0.9	0.9
1098	NCoT [J/(kg*m)]	5.4	7.9	5.6
1099	HR_{plateau} [beats/min]	145	142	147

1100 Key metabolic parameters assessment for the second circuit lap. Comparison among the three tested
1101 prosthetic feet.

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3.4 Questionnaires

Mean values and variability of the responses for each of the nine validated PEQ scales are presented in Table 5. The mobility scale, which includes ambulation and transfer tasks, yielded values of 72.1 ± 11.2 , 70.4 ± 10.4 , and 66.4 ± 10.6 for the SoftFoot Pro, Triton and original SoftFoot, respectively. Identical scores are recorded for all three prosthetic feet on the Frustration (76.9 ± 7.4), Perceived Response (94.3 ± 12.7), Residual Limb Health (31.8 ± 10.3), and Social Burden (76.8 ± 32.8) scales.

The basic, advanced, and total LCI-5 scores are recorded and reported in Table 6. Each prosthetic foot received a basic mobility score of 26 out of 28, an advanced mobility score of 25 out of 28, and a total score of 51 out of 56.

SUS results showed usability scores of 75, 60, and 75 out of 100 for the Triton, the original SoftFoot, and the SoftFoot Pro, respectively. For all three prosthetic feet, final values for each question of the questionnaire are reported on the left side of Fig. 7.

Results from the five-point Likert Scale NASA TLX survey for all three prosthetic feet are summarized on the right side of Fig. 7. The SoftFoot Pro is associated with the lowest reported values—2 out of 5—for mental demand, physical demand, performance effort, and frustration experienced by the participant. A peak value of 4 was reported

Table 5

Scales	Prosthetic feet		
	Triton	Original SoftFoot	SoftFoot Pro
Mobility (ambulation and transfer)	70.4 ± 10.4	66.4 ± 10.6	72.1 ± 11.2
Appearance	60.1 ± 27.6	57.9 ± 25.9	58.3 ± 26.1
Frustration	76.9 ± 7.4	76.9 ± 7.4	76.9 ± 7.4
Perceived response	94.3 ± 12.7	94.3 ± 12.7	94.3 ± 12.7
Residual limb health	31.8 ± 10.3	31.8 ± 10.3	31.8 ± 10.3
Social burden	76.8 ± 32.8	76.8 ± 32.8	76.8 ± 32.8
Sounds			
Utility	70.3 ± 13.8	68.8 ± 13.4	69 ± 13.3
Well-being	73.2 ± 2.2	70 ± 2.3	73.2 ± 2.2

Prosthetic Evaluation Questionnaire results: mean and standard deviation of the responses for the nine validated scales of the PEQ across the three tested prosthetic feet. The evaluation can not be performed for the Sounds scale.

1151 **Table 6**

	Prosthetic feet		
	Triton	Original SoftFoot	SoftFoot Pro
1155 Basic LCI-5	26	26	26
1156 Advanced LCI-5	25	25	25
1157 Overall LCI-5	51	51	51

1158 Locomotor Capability Index results: basic, advanced and overall LCI-5 scores across the three tested
 1159 prosthetic feet.

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1176 **Fig. 7** System Usability Scale and NASA Task Load Index results: on the left, SUS questionnaire
 1177 values for each of the questions; on the right, NASA TLX questionnaire values for each of the six
 1178 independent questions. Patterns are reported for the Triton (red), the original SoftFoot (green) and
 1179 the SoftFoot Pro (blue).

1180 for performance effort when using the Triton, while peak values of 4 were recorded for
 1181 frustration and physical demand with the original SoftFoot.
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1185 3.5 Cybathlon Performance

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1187 Table 7 reports the completion times recorded by the SoftFoot Pro team and the other
 1188 three finalists in the final race. Bench and Table tasks' time is also reported, while it
 1189 was not in our earlier analysis.
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1192 The SoftFoot Pro team achieved second place, following the first-place finish by the
 1193 Rehab Tech Leg team ¹. Both teams delivered outstanding performances, each failing
 1194

1195 ¹<https://cybathlon.com/en/teams/rehab-tech-leg>

Table 7

Tasks	Competing teams			
	SoftFoot Pro	Rehab Tech Leg	Ossur LX	Ossur bionics
Balance Beam	43	X	20	X
Stairs	34	27	X	X
Step Over	38	33	X	44
Slopes	25	22	21	32
Bench and Table	17	25	21	20
Wobbly Steps	7	6	6	X
High Step	13	12	13	16
Ladder	19	18	16	26
Cross Country	X	19	20	X
Hurdles	30	15	25	X

Results of the Leg Prosthesis Race final round at Cybathlon 2024. The table shows the performance of Team SoftFoot Pro and of the other three finalist teams. For each task, the shortest completion times are highlighted in green, while red crosses are reported for failed tasks.

only one task: Cross Country for SoftFoot Pro and Balance Beam for Rehab Tech Leg.

Notably, they were the only teams in the final to successfully complete the Stairs task.

All teams completed the Slopes, Bench and Table, High Step, and Ladder tasks.

In contrast, the Balance Beam, Stairs, and Cross Country tasks were the most challenging, with only two teams managing to complete them.

The SoftFoot Pro pilot delivered an outstanding performance in the Bench and Table task and recorded times comparable to the overall winner in the Wobbly Steps, High Step, and Ladder tasks. However, it was slower in the Stairs, Step Over, Slopes, and Hurdles tasks, ultimately completing the course in 226 seconds compared to Rehab Tech Leg’s 177 seconds. The Össur teams failed more tasks: Össur LX failed two tasks (Stairs and Step Over), while Össur Bionics failed five (Balance Beam, Stairs, Wobbly Steps, Cross Country, and Hurdles), placing third and fourth, respectively.

3.5.1 User observations

User feedback on the original SoftFoot and SoftFoot Pro was collected during training for Cybathlon 2024 and through post-competition comments. The pilot described the event as “a showcase to the world to present the SoftFoot project” expressing pride

1243 in completing the race and aiming to win. He viewed the project as a way to over-
1244 come limitations of conventional prosthetic feet and “return to the past” by regaining
1245 abilities like walking on uneven terrain and jumping. Regarding the wearability of the
1246 three prosthetic feet, the participant reported “No major differences were noted in
1247 ease of donning between the SoftFoot devices and the carbon fiber foot as this was
1248 influenced more by the socket than the foot design”. The pilot found the Triton — his
1249 daily-use prosthesis — better for slippery or unpredictable conditions due to famil-
1250 iarity, and also appreciated its lighter weight. However, he noted that the SoftFoot
1251 Pro’s energy return made it feel easier to lift during walking. Regarding the training
1252 pre-competition, he said “Initially, adapting to the SoftFoot devices was challenging,
1253 but with use, the SoftFoot Pro showed clear advantages in complex tasks, especially
1254 those involving agility such as squatting or navigating obstacles”.

1263 In the end, reflecting on the race, the pilot believed that his performance with
1264 the SoftFoot Pro had been superior to what he could have achieved with the Triton,
1265 based on his experience using the former in the race and the latter in daily life. He
1266 also noted its potential usefulness beyond competition, addressing similar challenges
1267 encountered in daily life.

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1273 **4 Discussion**

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1275 The 2024 edition of the Cybathlon acted as a catalyst for advancing research, push-
1276 ing the mechanical innovations of the original SoftFoot, and ultimately leading to the
1277 development of the latest state-of-the-art model of the SoftFoot Pro. Moreover, the
1278 event provided a unique opportunity to evaluate the SoftFoot Pro in a competitive
1279 environment, alongside both research and commercially available prosthetic foot sys-
1280 tems. Both the qualification phase and the final round of the competition provided a
1281 tangible opportunity to showcase the innovation of the SoftFoot Pro in terms of adapt-
1282 ability to various obstacles. The prosthesis also proved highly versatile, enabling the
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pilot to negotiate the full range of tasks and challenges presented by the race effectively. Moreover, the prosthesis worked seamlessly with a commercial knee, with no need for any specific adjustment. In qualifications, the pilot scored the maximum 100 points, completing all tasks successfully and placing second only due to a slower time. In the final, the pilot again delivered an excellent performance, earning 90 points, the same as the winning team, and securing second place. This result reflected the mechanical improvements of the SoftFoot Pro, the team's efforts during training, and the pilot's commitment, consistency, and perseverance.

In preparation for the competition, the participant, an individual with a unilateral transfemoral amputation, underwent extensive training with the SoftFoot Pro, the original SoftFoot, and a commercial carbon fiber foot. The extensive familiarization period with both SoftFoot models ensured a fair and informed comparison between prosthetic solutions. The participant reported clear advantages with the SoftFoot Pro over both the original SoftFoot and his habitual commercial prosthesis, and chose it as his preferred device for the official competition.

Level Walking

The kinematic analysis of level walking was performed during a training session by assessing the ankle, knee, and hip angles in the sagittal plane. The subject walked using the three prosthetic feet: his commercial carbon fiber foot (a Triton by Ottobock), the original SoftFoot, and the SoftFoot Pro. Each prosthesis resulted in distinct movement patterns. However, all devices shared a common limitation, which consisted of the reduction or absence of plantarflexion during the push-off phase. Such a limitation compromises forward propulsion and overall gait efficiency. Nonetheless, this lack could be the result of the prosthetic knee functionality, which was the same for all the feet. Additionally, all devices consistently exhibited a lack of dorsiflexion during the swing phase, resulting in reduced foot-ground clearance compared to the biological data. This was attributed to the fact that all the tested devices were passive and lacked an ankle

1335 mechanism capable of generating active torque. The subject tends to increase hip and
1336 knee flexion as a compensatory strategy, altering the biomechanics of walking. This
1337 is evident in the excessive hip flexion (see Fig. 4) compared to unimpaired subjects,
1338 further confirming an inefficient and asymmetric gait.
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1341 Although we highlighted these limitations across all tested prosthetic devices, some
1342 important differences emerged among them, potentially resulting in different perfor-
1343 mance levels for each foot. One key distinction of the SoftFoot Pro lies in the insertion
1344 of an ankle joint, which is connected to the pylon via a shank link. This configura-
1345 tion allows the rear and anterior arches to rotate more freely around the ankle joint,
1346 enabling a greater range of motion relative to the prosthetic pylon. As a result, this
1347 increased mobility facilitates the generation of greater torque in response to the force
1348 applied by the user during walking. Additionally, the SoftFoot Pro enables a more effi-
1349 cient reverse transmission of the mechanical action from the springs back to the user.
1350 Evidence supporting this can be seen in Fig. 4, which shows increased plantarflexion
1351 and dorsiflexion at the beginning (6%) and near the end of the stance phase (45%),
1352 compared to the other two prosthetic feet. This enhanced motion allows for a more
1353 natural and symmetric gait, more closely replicating the plantarflexion and dorsiflex-
1354 ion peaks during stance observed in the sound ankle and resembling the pattern of
1355 an unimpaired subject. In contrast, the absence of an ankle joint in the original Soft-
1356 Foot limits the independent rotation of the arches relative to the pylon, resulting in a
1357 restricted range of motion (reduced plantarflexion and dorsiflexion peaks) throughout
1358 the stance phase. Consequently, the gait produced with this foot appears less symmet-
1359 ric, with differences in amplitude, particularly during the dorsiflexion phase at the end
1360 of the stance, showing 8° in the prosthetic ankle compared to 13° in the sound ankle.
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1363 Another challenge faced by the prosthetic user, with the previously described pros-
1364 thesis and the three prosthetic feet tested, is the absence of an early-stance knee flexion
1365 peak in the prosthetic limb, which is essential for shock absorption in unimpaired
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gait and may indicate reduced dynamic balance during walking (see Fig. 4). Furthermore, the slight but unexpected knee hyperextension observed just before the swing phase (approximately 30%–50% of the gait cycle) when the user is wearing the original SoftFoot, may represent a compensatory strategy adopted by the user to counteract the limited dorsiflexion amplitude achieved by the corresponding ankle joint during the same phase of stance. However, further studies are needed to confirm and more thoroughly characterize this compensatory mechanism.

In light of the considerations outlined above, we can observe that, when the user is wearing the original SoftFoot, greater differences between the sound and prosthetic limbs emerge in both the amplitude and pattern of joint angles — particularly at the more distal joints.

This increased asymmetry in limb behavior results in reduced overall gait efficiency, a less symmetric gait pattern, and higher energy expenditure. These findings are supported by the metabolic analysis, which shows higher oxygen consumption (VO_2), and Net Cost of Transport (NCoT) values associated with the use of the original SoftFoot. This is an expected result, as the original SoftFoot is missing an energy-storing and returning cycle, thus providing a very poor torque during push-off, compared to the Triton, which acts as a spring, and the SoftFoot Pro, which exploits the agonist-antagonist mechanism.

Furthermore, the limited range of plantarflexion and dorsiflexion during stance using the original SoftFoot explains the small ROM value experienced at the prosthetic ankle, compared to the Triton foot and the SoftFoot Pro. Additionally, the lack of energy storage and return in the original SoftFoot determines a lack of power generation during the push-off phase of walking, contributing to the shorter stride length and walking velocity, as reported in Table 2. In contrast, the aforementioned freedom of relative motion between the rear and front arches and the pylon, enabled by the ankle joint of the SoftFoot Pro, provides greater ankle mobility during gait not only

1427 compared to the original SoftFoot, but also surpassing that of the Triton, as shown in
1428 Fig. 5 and Table 1. When adopting the SoftFoot Pro, the subject demonstrates stride
1429 length and average gait speed comparable with those of the Triton and greater than
1430 those achieved with the original SoftFoot. These effects are attributed to the springs
1431 of the agonist-antagonist ankle. Together, these components allow for greater energy
1432 storage during the stance phase and a more efficient return during push-off compared
1433 to the original SoftFoot, enhancing forward propulsion.
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1437 *Stairs task*

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1439 The stairs task was the only Cybathlon task with an in-depth kinematic analysis of the
1440 lower limb joint, as it is considered one of the standard gait modes in the literature.
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1442 When analyzing the findings for the unimpaired subject and the performance of the
1443 carbon fiber Triton foot, the kinematic results for both stair ascent and descent were
1444 consistent with findings previously reported in the literature [31, 32]. Regarding the
1445 sagittal joint angle patterns of the original SoftFoot and SoftFoot Pro, the observed
1446 trends align with those documented in the literature, while still preserving the benefits
1447 associated with the soft sole design. According to user feedback, during stair descent,
1448 the SoftFoot designs offer enhanced control, thanks to the flexible toes that adapt to
1449 the geometry of the steps. In stair ascent, although the Triton foot initially required less
1450 effort due to its higher energy return compared to the original SoftFoot, this advantage
1451 was offset by the performance of the SoftFoot Pro. Thanks to its greater ankle range of
1452 motion, the SoftFoot Pro ultimately emerged as a potentially more suitable option for
1453 stair ascent. As a general observation, the tested prostheses have a marginal impact
1454 on proximal joint behavior. As we can deduce from Fig. 4, both during the ascent
1455 and the descent phases, the three prosthetic feet exhibited sagittal plane joint angle
1456 patterns at the prosthetic limb with increased differences as the joints are more distal.
1457 Kinematic results highlighted that the most pronounced differences among the three
1458 prosthetic feet were observed at the prosthetic ankle during the stance phase of the
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descent task, particularly between 0% and 40% of the gait cycle, where dorsiflexion varied notably in both angle trend and peak values across steps and between devices. However, the data variability among the three steps for each foot, mainly observable at the prosthetic knee and hip during stairs ascent, affects all joint angle patterns. It results in significant changes and discrepancies in the gait cycle events timing. The explanation of this variability can be the subject's approach to the task, aiming to complete it as quickly as possible while avoiding dropping the cup or committing any other infractions that could lead to disqualification, rather than focusing on the precise repetition of the movement.

Furthermore, the increased range of motion observed at the joints of the sound limb — particularly at the intact ankle — during stair ascent and descent suggests a compensatory strategy to counteract the limited mobility of the prosthetic ankle across all three feet. This finding is consistent with typical hip compensation strategies in individuals with transfemoral amputation, where the absence of a propulsive push-off phase, due to reduced plantarflexion and lack of active knee, is offset by a greater load on the sound limb and increased hip flexion on the prosthetic side to facilitate proper foot placement on the next step. In the Cybathlon setting, this compensation is amplified by the pilot's focus on speed of task completion over optimal use of prosthetic ROM, contributing to high variability in joint angles across steps and devices. Despite reduced ankle ROM in all prostheses, the SoftFoot Pro still showed the highest ROM during both ascent and descent.

Cybathlon

The kinematic and metabolic evaluations conducted on the Cybathlon tasks from the 2024 Cybathlon edition focus on assessing performance in 9 out of the 10 tasks with the three prosthetic feet. The fact that the subject performs the circuit at race speed in preparation for the Cybathlon event, adhering to the competition rules, reduced,

1519 indeed, the repeatability of the tasks, making a task-specific kinematic analysis com-
1520 plex. Moreover, the scope of this study was to provide an overview of the prosthetic
1521 behavior during daily-life tasks, and not to analyze a specific activity.
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1524 1525 *Maximum angular excursion*

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1527 Angular excursion analysis across Cybathlon tasks shows that, in most cases, the
1528 SoftFoot Pro consistently outperforms the original SoftFoot and the Triton at the
1529 prosthetic ankle. However, differences are less evident in the High Step and Cross
1530 Country tasks, which prioritize stability over ankle motion. In the High Step task, the
1531 foot starts flat on the ground and finishes flat on the obstacle when stepping on it,
1532 while in the Cross Country task, precision of movement is required to avoid touching
1533 the floor, a condition that would invalidate the task. For this reason, the use of ankle
1534 ROM was limited, and the differences between devices were minimized. The elevated
1535 peak hip flexion across Cybathlon tasks, compared to typical level walking, is due to
1536 trunk bending for object pickup and high thigh elevation to clear obstacles. This is
1537 supported by the noticeably lower hip flexion in the Wobbly Steps task, which involves
1538 only walking on unstable surfaces without object handling or obstacle clearance.
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1541 1542 *Completion times*

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1544 The SoftFoot Pro enabled faster walking than the original SoftFoot Pro and matched
1545 the Triton in level walking speed. However, its adaptability, combined with the energy
1546 recycling, led to faster overall performance in diverse daily activities, as shown by
1547 shorter Cybathlon track completion times — even when compared to the Triton. It
1548 outperformed the other feet in nearly all individual tasks, except for the Stairs, Ladder,
1549 and Cross Country tasks, where the strategy adopted to complete the task and the
1550 precision in lower limb movements mattered more than speed.
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<i>Metabolic cost</i>	1565
Finally, the SoftFoot Pro was analyzed in terms of the energy cost required by the	1566
subject to complete the experiment, considering both the resting phase and the exe-	1567
cution of two laps of the Cybathlon circuit. The presence of springs that mimic the	1568
function of human muscles and tendons allows for energy storage during the initial	1569
part of the stance phase, replicating the action of dorsiflexor muscles—primarily the	1570
tibialis anterior—and enables increased energy release during push-off, emulating the	1571
function of plantarflexor muscles and the Achilles tendon. The use of the SoftFoot	1572
Pro resulted in an energy expenditure for the user that matched that required when	1573
using the Triton, as indicated by similar values of oxygen consumption (VO_2) and net	1574
metabolic cost of transport (NCoT), and lower than the energy expenditure observed	1575
with the original SoftFoot. Its design feature, together with the observed results, sup-	1576
ports the hypothesis that the energy-recycling mechanism of the agonist-antagonist	1577
joint reduces user effort and the need for compensatory movements compared to the	1578
original SoftFoot. Moreover, all three prosthetic feet showed a RER value consistently	1579
lower than 1, indicating that the subject produces less carbon dioxide than the oxygen	1580
consumed to complete the experiment, suggesting a predominant reliance on aerobic	1581
metabolism.	1582
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<i>Subjective feedback</i>	1596
The results of this study are consistent and further supported by the participant’s	1597
informal feedback, as well as by the outcomes of the evaluation questionnaires. Among	1598
the administered questionnaires, the LCI-5 and PEQ include items specifically related	1599
to locomotor abilities. Notably, the most promising outcomes emerge from the PEQ,	1600
where the user reported greater mobility impressions when using the SoftFoot Pro.	1601
Additional insights are provided by the NASA-TLX questionnaire, where the user	1602
indicated lower mental and physical demand when walking with the SoftFoot Pro	1603
compared to the other devices.	1604
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1611 *Study Limitations and Future Directions*

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1613 To strengthen the findings of this pilot investigation - conducted on a single par-
1614 ticipant, the official Cybathlon competitor - a greater number of subjects should be
1615 included in future studies, enabling statistical analysis to more robustly support the
1616 conclusions drawn. Additionally, to address the limitations of this study related to
1617 data variability and the reduced repeatability of the stair ascent and descent task,
1618 future evaluations should consider the use of a staircase with a greater number of
1619 consecutive steps. Future developments of this research will include the integration of
1620 electromyographic (EMG) analysis to assess lower limb muscle activation in relation
1621 to the metabolic cost of performing Cybathlon tasks.

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1623 Despite the SoftFoot Pro being designed according to the biomechanical require-
1624 ments of level walking, it showed a consistent performance across the diverse activities
1625 of the Cybathlon 2024 Leg Race. This might stem from the combination of the adapt-
1626 ability to the ground, the implementation of an ankle joint, and the agonist-antagonist
1627 mechanism. Moreover, its compact design makes it suitable for daily life; as reported by
1628 the user, after an adaptation period, both SoftFoot versions outperformed the Triton
1629 in tasks requiring bending and standing up, as their toe flexion reduced the user-to-
1630 ground distance, improving balance and reducing fall risk, benefits not possible with
1631 rigid carbon fiber soles.

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1634 **5 Conclusion**

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1636 In this paper, we analyzed and compared the kinematics, metabolic cost, and per-
1637 formance of a single subject performing the Cybathlon 2024 Leg Race, with three
1638 different prosthetic devices: the Triton foot, the original SoftFoot, and the SoftFoot
1639 Pro. The agonist-antagonist SoftFoot Pro demonstrated significant advancements over
1640 the original SoftFoot, combining enhanced mechanical functionality with improved
1641 metabolic efficiency. This device was designed to add the energy recycling property of
1642

the carbon fiber feet, keeping the adaptability of the original SoftFoot. Its use during both the completion of challenging tasks from the Cybathlon 2024 competition and level walking highlighted an increased ankle joint range of motion enabled by the integrated revolute joint. Furthermore, the energy storage and return feature, enabled through anterior and posterior springs mimicking the function of agonist-antagonist muscles and tendons, contributed to a noticeable reduction in the subject's effort, improving overall metabolic performance. This was supported by lower oxygen consumption (VO_2) and net metabolic cost of transport (NCoT), which were comparable to the values obtained with the subject's regular carbon fiber foot and significantly better than those recorded with the original SoftFoot. The participation of the SoftFoot Pro in the official Cybathlon 2024 Leg Prosthesis Race, along with the excellent performance of its pilot, further highlighted the potential of this experimental device. These results, supported by the user's observations and qualitative feedback, suggested that the SoftFoot Pro could represent a promising alternative to existing commercial energy-storing and returning carbon fiber prosthetic feet, combining the energy recycling property with the adaptability to the ground.

List of abbreviations

SACH: Solid Ankle Cushioned Heel	1657
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ESR: Energy Storage and Return	1689
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IMU: Inertial Measurement Units	1691
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PEQ: Prosthetic Evaluation Questionnaire	1693
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LCI: Locomotor Capabilities Index	1695
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SUS: System Usability Scale	1697
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NASA TLX: NASA Task Load Index	1699
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LW: Level Walking	1701
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U: Stair Ascent	

1703 D: Stair Descent
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1705 IL: Intact Limb
1706 PL: Prosthetic Limb
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1708 ROM: Range of Motion
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1710 BH: Body Height
1711 RER: Respiratory Exchange Ratio
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1713 NCoT: Net Cost of Transport
1714
1715 EEq: Energetic Equivalent
1716 RMR: Resting Metabolic Rate
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1718 WS: Walking Speed
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1720 HR: Heart Rate
1721 EMG: Electromyography
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1724 **Supplementary information**
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1727 **Additional file 1**
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1729 *File format:* MP4 video (.mp4)

1730 *Description of data:* This video illustrates the fitting process of the SoftFoot Pro
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1732 prosthesis, its integration into the participant's daily life, and its application during
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1734 both training and the official Cybathlon Leg race competition.

1735
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1744 constant participation, enthusiasm, and keen interest in the project.

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Declarations	1749
	1750
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Competing interests. The authors declare that they have no competing interests.	1755 1756
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Consent for publication. The participant signed consent for publication.	1764 1765 1766
Availability of data and materials. The dataset generated and the analysis code are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.	1767 1768 1769
Author contribution. SM Conceptualization, software, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, visualization, writing – original draft preparation, writing—review and editing.	1770 1771 1772 1773 1774
MC (Matteo Crotti) Conceptualization, software, investigation, visualization, writing – review and editing.	1775 1776 1777 1778
AP Conceptualization, software, investigation, visualization, writing – review and editing.	1779 1780 1781
GG Conceptualization, methodology, project administration, visualization, writing – review and editing.	1782 1783 1784
AB Conceptualization, funding acquisition, resources, writing – review and editing, project administration.	1785 1786 1787
MC (Maura Casadio) Conceptualization, supervision, writing – review and editing.	1788 1789
MGC Conceptualization, funding acquisition, writing—review and editing, methodology, project administration.	1790 1791 1792
MGC, MC (Matteo Crotti), AP were part of the team at the Cybathlon.	1793 1794

1795 All authors contributed to the manuscript. All authors read and agreed to the
1796 published version of the manuscript.
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Supplementary Files

This is a list of supplementary files associated with this preprint. Click to download.

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